

Thiophthalic Acids. Part I.

BY GOPÁL CHANDRA CHAKRAVARTI.

Various attempts have been made since 1874 to synthesise two important acids, *viz.*, mono- and di-thiophthalic acids. But up till now these endeavours have proved fruitless. In 1874 Schreder (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 704) treated phenyl phthalate in alcoholic solution with potassium hydrosulphide and appears to have obtained a very impure potassium thiophthalate from which hydrochloric acid set free the body $C_8H_4O_2S$. This body corresponds with thiophthalic anhydride and not with the acids. He represented the reaction by the following equations:—

In 1884 Graebe and Zschokke (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1175) found that thiophthalic anhydride and not the acid is obtained by acidification of the solution obtained by slowly adding phthalic chloride to a cold concentrated solution of sodium hydrogen sulphide. Later Reissert and Holle (*Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3027) prepared a number of derivatives of both mono- and di-thiophthalic acids starting from thiophthalic anhydride but concluded like the previous investigators that these acids were somewhat stable in the form of their alkali salts in aqueous solutions, whereas the free acids were extremely unstable and therefore could not be obtained as such, the acids decomposing immediately into thiophthalic anhydride, m. p. 114°, and hydrogen sulphide.

Recently the author (Chakravarti and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 141) made an attempt to condense phthalic anhydride with aromatic mercaptans in order to obtain dyes analogous to the phthaleins but found that the great reactivity of the mercaptanic hydrogen atoms led to the formation of thiophthalic esters instead

of the thiophthalic acids. In that communication the authors expressed their intention of utilising the thiophthalates for the syntheses of mono- and di-thiophthalic acids. By carrying out the hydrolysis of ditolyl-dithiophthalate with alcoholic potassium hydrosulphide under various conditions, an acid containing sulphur and melting at 242° with decomposition was obtained. The acid however did not respond to the ordinary tests for 'thiol' group and the determination of its equivalent weight showed that it had a molecular weight almost double that required by monothiophthalic acid and was therefore dithio-dibenzoyl-*o*:*o*'-dicarboxylic acid (II).

The formation of this acid at once suggested that at an intermediate stage monothiophthalic acid must have been produced, and the latter might be obtained if the reaction could be properly moderated. But at a lower temperature the hydrolysis of the thioester would not take place. Hence a study of the interaction of potassium hydrosulphide and phthalyl chloride in alcoholic solution seemed desirable. It was found that the reaction proceeds very briskly even in the cold and from the products a number of compounds together with monothiophthalic acid have been isolated. A description of these products and their method of isolation are given in the experimental portion. From a study of the properties of monothiophthalic acid, the author generally agrees with the views expressed by previous investigators about the extreme unstability of the acid, but the hypothesis that it breaks down immediately on formation into thiophthalic anhydride should once for all be discarded. Because under ordinary conditions the anhydride was never obtained by the decomposition of the acid; the product that was invariably obtained was the corresponding disulphide, dithio-dibenzoyl dicarboxylic acid, evidently formed by the oxidation of the mercaptanic hydrogen atom. In fact the acid is so very reactive towards oxygen that it gets oxidised by the atmosphere even during processes of purification and crystallisation; so that for a long time the disulphide was looked upon as the initial product of the reaction.

In the operations a sample of crystallised potassium hydrosulphide supplied by Kahlbaum was used. As this contains water of

crystallisation it is very difficult to indicate the exact mechanism of the reaction, which may have taken either of the courses:—

or

Of the two alternatives, reaction (1) appears to be the more likely, because although the dithio acid has not been isolated in the pure state its existence has been confirmed from various facts. The extract obtained by aqueous carbonated alkalis from the ethereal solution of the reaction product on acidification gives a precipitate of the monothio acid or more generally its disulphide mixed with an acidic oil with very strong characteristic disagreeable odour. This oily acid gradually diminishes in quantity during purification and more and more of the solid acid is produced. This change therefore represents the second phase of reaction (1). Moreover, when the ethereal solution of the mixture of acids or their aqueous alkaline solution is kept exposed to the air for sometime a yellow precipitate insoluble in alkalis begins to appear which can only be formed by the elimination of hydrogen sulphide from dithiophthalic acid or of alkaline sulphides from its alkaline solutions:

In fact when such an alkaline solution is acidified after removal of the yellow precipitate, hydrogen sulphide is evolved plentifully and simultaneously thiophthalic anhydride also is formed in considerable quantity by the elimination of one molecule of hydrogen sulphide from a molecule of the acid. Thus dithiophthalic acid undergoes a threefold decomposition into monothiophthalic acid, thiophthalic anhydride and diphthalyl disulphide. The crude acid could not be purified from admixture with solvents and the monothio acid on account of its extreme instability and is under further investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

12 Gm. of potassium hydrosulphide are mixed with 125 c.c. of absolute alcohol and saturated with sulphuretted hydrogen in the cold and then gradually added to a cold solution of 15 gm. of phthalyl chloride in 75 c.c. of alcohol. A vigorous reaction at once begins. The reaction-bottle is well-corked, cooled by a freezing mixture to -5° and allowed to stand for half an hour with occasional shaking. Then the vessel is removed to a shaking machine and the reaction is allowed to proceed there for about three hours at a temperature not exceeding 10° , and then the mixture allowed to stand overnight. The contents of the bottle are next poured on to about a litre of ice water and the aqueous mixture extracted with ether. The ethereal extract is washed thoroughly with cold water and then neutralised with a slight excess of a cold solution of sodium carbonate. A yellow precipitate (A) which is neither soluble in alkali nor in ether separates out at this stage and is removed. The ethereal extract (B) is kept for further treatment.

A part of the alkaline extract is neutralised with cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the precipitated stuff extracted with ether. This ethereal solution is dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and on slow evaporation deposits needle-shaped crystals, which are found to be difficultly soluble in ether. The product is therefore crystallised from a large quantity of absolute alcohol and obtained in the form of very light cream-coloured minute crystals, melting about 242° with decomposition. These are found to correspond to dithio-dibenzoyl *o*:*o*'-dicarboxylic acid. (Found: C, 52.91; H, 2.84; S, 17.98. $C_{16}H_{10}O_6S_2$ requires C, 53.04; H, 2.76; S, 17.9 per cent.). The *potassium salt* is prepared by adding the calculated quantity of alcoholic caustic potash to an absolute alcoholic solution of the acid and evaporating part of the alcohol in vacuum. (Found: K, 18.01. $C_{16}H_8O_6S_2K_2$ requires K, 17.8 per cent.). The *lead salt* is obtained as a white crystalline precipitate by adding lead acetate solution to a solution of the potassium salt in water. The precipitate is washed with water, alcohol and ether. (Found: Pb, 36.15. $C_{16}H_8O_6S_2Pb$ requires Pb, 36.5 per cent.). The remaining portion of the alkaline extract was converted into the lead salt by means of lead acetate solution and the lead salt washed with water and alcohol and thoroughly dried. The powdered lead compound is suspended in anhydrous ether and decomposed by passing sulphuretted hydrogen.

The precipitate of lead sulphide is filtered off and the ethereal solution on concentration deposits almost colourless needle-shaped crystals of monothiophthalic acid which after recrystallisation from ether melts with decomposition at about 193°. (Found: C, 52.22; H, 3.8; S, 17.24. $C_8H_4O_3S$ requires C, 52.74; H, 3.28; S, 17.56 per cent.). Monothiophthalic acid is readily soluble in ether and alcohol. Its conversion into the less soluble disulphide is so rapid in presence of air that even during the evaporation of its ethereal solution it gets oxidised so that in the course of several preparations the disulphide dicarboxylic acid was the only compound obtained in the final stage. The ethereal mother-liquor, after removal of the monothio acid, leaves an oil with strongly acid character and characteristic disagreeable odour. From preliminary investigation this oil-acid is supposed to be dithiophthalic acid. Further investigation is in progress.

The sodium salt of monothiophthalic acid is obtained by adding the calculated quantity of aqueous sodium carbonate solution to an alcoholic solution of the acid. The filtered solution is concentrated to a small bulk, treated with absolute alcohol and again filtered. On keeping in contact with a small quantity of ether, the solution deposits colourless crystals of the sodium salt. (Found: Na, 20.10. $C_8H_4O_3SNa_2$ requires Na, 20.3 per cent.). The lead salt is obtained by adding an alcoholic lead acetate solution to an alcoholic solution of the acid. (Found: Pb, 53.21. $C_8H_4O_3SPb$ requires Pb, 53.48 per cent.).

The yellow precipitate (A) is washed with water, dried and repeatedly extracted with a large volume of alcohol. The alcohol removes a quantity of sulphur only. The deep yellow residue is dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot pyridine, which deposits on cooling a crop of very light needle-shaped egg yellow crystals which do not decompose on heating up to 320°. The compound is insoluble in ether, alcohol, benzene, etc., and in alkalis and is supposed to be diphthalyl disulphide. (Found: S, 19.26. $C_{16}H_8O_4S_2$ requires S, 19.51 per cent.).

The ethereal solution (B) is dehydrated with anhydrous magnesium sulphate and then slowly evaporated. Colourless needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 114°, are obtained. They are identical with thiophthalic anhydride. (Found: S, 19.42. $C_8H_4O_3S$ requires S, 19.51 per cent.). The ethereal mother-liquor, on complete evaporation, leaves an oil which is purified from admixed solid by distillation in steam.

The distillate is extracted with ether, dehydrated by anhydrous magnesium sulphate, filtered and the ether completely removed first on the water-bath and finally in a vacuum over sulphuric acid. The constitution of the oil has not been determined.

Hydrolysis of Ditolyl-dithiophthalate : Formation of Dithiodibenzoyl-o : o'-dicarboxylic Acid.—10 Gm. ditolyldithiophthalate and 7 gm. of potassium hydrosulphide are suspended in 75 c.c. of absolute alcohol and saturated with sulphuretted hydrogen. The mixture is heated in a sealed tube for 8—9 hours at 120°. The red solution is partially evaporated, treated with water and the aqueous solution decanted off from the insoluble oil, cooled by ice and treated with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated mass is next treated with sodium carbonate solution and the solution washed with ether, filtered and reprecipitated with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid is washed with water and crystallised from absolute alcohol. Cream-coloured needle-shaped crystals, m.p. 242° d. identical with those of dithiodibenzoyl-o : o'-dicarboxylic acid are obtained.

I desire to thank Sir P. C. Rây for his very kind interest and also Mr. R. K. Bhattacharyya, M.Sc., A.I.I.Sc. for rendering valuable help in the analytical work.

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received May 7, 1938.